

SURVEILLANCE CARD_CCHF_Pathogen detection in ticks collected from domestic ruminants in high-risk regions

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in ticks collected from domestic ruminants in high-risk regions.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen. Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread to new areas.
3	Target species and group	<i>Hyalomma spp. ticks</i> (mainly <i>H. marginatum</i>).
4	Target sector / production type	Domestic ruminants with exposure to ticks (all sectors).
5	Geographical area covered	High risk areas with regards to introduction of disease (close to endemic areas) and presence of ticks (climate, vegetation). Areas with suspected presence of CCHF or which have previously been endemic to CCHF.
6	Age group	Adult ticks.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Collecting ticks can be combined with the surveillance component "CCHF – serological surveillance of domestic ruminants in high-risk areas".
8	Sampling time period	Vector period (spring to autumn).
9	Sampling matrix	Adult <i>Hyalomma spp.</i> Ticks.
10	Type of disease indicators	Virus.
11	Sampling unit	Ticks and animals.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Convenience sampling, ticks can be collected from animals under surveillance in other surveillance components.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Pooling by animal/location/life stage –pool of max 5 half ticks (other half for virus isolation). Antigen testing by RT-PCR.

14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component can contribute to the early detection of introduction of the virus in new areas. However, results cannot be used directly for estimation of detection sensitivity or confidence of freedom since this is a biased (non-representative) sample of an unknown population.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Not applicable.
18	References	<p>1) Cicculi V, Maitre A, Ayhan N, Mondoloni S, Paoli JC, Vial L, de Lamballerie XN, Charrel R, Falchi A. Lack of Evidence for Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus in Ticks Collected from Animals, Corsica, France. <i>Emerg Infect Dis.</i> 2022 May;28(5):1035-1038. doi: 10.3201/eid2805.211996. PMID: 35447051; PMCID: PMC9045455.</p> <p>2) Mazzola LT, Kelly-Cirino C. Diagnostic tests for Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever: a widespread tickborne disease. <i>BMJ Glob Health.</i> 2019 Feb 20;4(Suppl 2):e001114. doi: 10.1136/bmjgh-2018-001114. PMID: 30899574; PMCID: PMC6407549.</p>
19	Additional comments	The rate of CCHFV-infected ticks in countries in Europe with enzootic foci ranges from 0.50% to 3.70% among <i>Hyalomma</i> spp. ticks (1)